

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOLERS

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Annotation: the article considers an urgent problem of environmental protection - the formation of the beginning of ecological culture in children; the formation of a consciously correct attitude to objects and phenomena of nature; to develop ecological thinking; training in practical actions for nature protection.

Keywords: ecology, environmental education, the importance of ecology, environmental education.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of "Ecology" and everything related to it has forever entered our everyday vocabulary, but it is understood in different ways. From a scientific point of view, there are many definitions. One of the most common: ecology is the science of the relationship between living organisms and the environment.

Environmental education is the education of love for nature. This is a really important part of the parenting process, but often the techniques used to foster such love are very questionable. For example: people can keep wild animals at home, which should live in the wild. Or they keep pets without proper care: allowing them to get sick or die in front of children. Children understand that this is a normal situation, they get used to not noticing their torment. Very often in summer, during walks, adults suggest picking flowers, catching dragonflies, butterflies, ladybirds or other insects. And then for a long time it becomes a constant fun for children in the summer. They can tear off the insect's wings, paws, or even trample it with their foot. Such "educational activities" teach children not to love, but to brutally destroy life.

Still, it is necessary to teach environmentally correct behavior. One of the tasks of environmental education is to form in children the idea of man not as the master, the ruler of nature, but as a part of nature dependent on it. It is necessary to set a goal for ourselves - to eradicate the consumer attitude towards nature in children.

Nowadays, most preschool children have a clear division of animals into "bad" and "good", "evil" and "kind", "harmful" and "useful". It is necessary to teach children that, being in nature, you can not pick plants for a bouquet. Collect medicinal plants only in places where there are many of them. Being in the forest, it is necessary to walk strictly along the paths so that the plants do not die from trampling. It is necessary to protect not only rare, but also other plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Works of art, fairy tales, and cartoons can contribute to proper environmental education. Fiction about nature deeply affects the feelings of children (these are the works of F. Tyutchev, A. Pushkin, N. Nekrasov, A. Feta, K. Ushinsky, L. Tolstoy, M. Prishvin, V. Bianchi, N. Sladkova).

In fairy tales and some cartoons, predatory animals are depicted as "evil", bad. They want to offend or eat small defenseless bunnies and piglets. Basically, the "weak" defeat the evil predators. Many children understand this in such a way that a predatory beast is "evil" and bad, it is not needed by nature and should not live in the forest. The forest is beautiful even without such animals (without predators). But ecology tells us that there are no "good" or "bad", "useful" or "harmful" in nature. Every living thing, be it a plant or an animal, an insect, etc., does its "job", has its own role in nature. But how poor our nature has become: some species of plants and animals have become rare. The forests were very rich in mushrooms and berries, but now they are no longer there. The fertile particles of the earth are destroyed, the atmospheric air is polluted by exhaust gases, water emissions from factories and sewage drains.

"To a fish - water, to a bird - air, to an animal - forest, steppes, mountains. And a man needs a Homeland. And protecting nature means protecting the Homeland." That's what the Russian writer Mikhail Prishvin said.

Environmental education of children is primarily the instilling of humanity, kindness, respect for nature and all living things. It is necessary to show children by their own example how to treat nature: do not leave garbage in recreation areas, do not throw garbage on the move, do not offend homeless animals, do not pick flowers, do not chop down trees, do not break anthills, feed birds in winter.

In preschool institutions, it is necessary to hold parent-teacher meetings on the topic "Tasks of environmental education", a round table "Fostering kindness to

nature", conversations with children on environmental protection. To post newsletters on the topic "Respect for nature". To talk in class about the Red Book, why certain species of plants and animals disappear. Conduct didactic games with children to familiarize themselves with trees and shrubs; vegetables and fruits; with animals and their cubs. Organize duty in a corner of nature and work on sites. To go on excursions, to reveal to children the diversity and beauty of the surrounding world. Organize a vegetable garden and flower garden on the site: sow seeds, loosen the ground, spray, water. Select plants so that during the season some flowers are replaced by others.

In kindergartens, it is necessary to hold contests for children's drawings "How I spent the summer", "Seasons", "Leaf fall", "Winter-winter"; craft contests. Children would try to involve their parents, grandparents, brothers and sisters in making crafts at home.

To create an "ecological trail" in preschool institutions, which allows you to use simple walks for environmental activities and at the same time helps to improve children's health in the fresh air. The "Ecological Trail" is the sensory development of children, a place for systematic observations, games, and environmental celebrations. Many modern children rarely communicate with nature, but environmental education begins with getting to know the objects around them that preschoolers encounter every day.

Revealing the beauty of nature to children and teaching them to see it is not an easy task. To do this, the educator himself must be able to live in harmony with nature!

At preschool age, children show an active interest in everything, they constantly have a desire to do something, explore the world around them. The development of interests and abilities of preschoolers leads to the formation of arbitrary behavior. One of the important tasks in early education is the knowledge of nature as a source of impressions and experience, the basis for solving problems, finding answers, and asking questions. Every day, children get a lot of impressions at home, on the playground, walking, excursions and, of course, in kindergarten. The harmonious development of a child is impossible without a comprehensive knowledge of the world around him, an understanding of the union of man and nature. This provides for a new pre-school education program, which focuses on the need to "... build children's knowledge about the social, natural and technical

environment; develop the ability to express their thoughts in a way that is understandable to others; give children a chance to learn, stimulating their curiosity, activity and independence; and also form those knowledge and abilities that are important for school education.". The program stimulates all areas of the child's activity. Interest in the world around them forces children to act and think independently. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically immerse preschoolers in experiment and observation.

The interest of children will tell you how to organize classes so that preschoolers have an internal motivation for new discoveries. In their understanding of learning, educators should rely on activating, practical, problematic, expressive forms of work, including educational games. The generally accepted organizational forms of environmental education include excursions, walks, design of a green corner, and participation in environmental actions. Outdoor activities simplify the process of observing the cyclical changes of the seasons. Walks promote group integration and socialization of children, introduce children to the flora and fauna.

It is recommended to use a variety of textbooks for environmental education of preschoolers. In addition to direct interaction with materials and objects of the surrounding world, it is advisable to use various illustrations, photographs, audio and video recordings, albums, books. They stimulate imagination, observation, and develop concentration and cognitive processes in children. A variety of tools is necessary to work with children with developmental delays. The material will be better absorbed if all the senses are involved.

Preschoolers have

unusually versatile perceptual abilities. They strive to learn not only with the help of their senses, but as if with their whole "body". For example, when a tree is studied in a group, children not only look at or touch it, but also lean against it, hug it, i.e. they act with their whole body. It is desirable to give children freedom, however, the activity of preschoolers must be monitored.

Getting rich impressions from communicating with nature, children ask many questions that adults should not neglect. The desire to satisfy interest mobilizes parents and caregivers to seek information and find interesting solutions.

If the child does not receive an answer to his question, there is a danger that the child will turn away from his observations. His "inability to understand" will then turn into an "unwillingness to understand."

The child has every right to an individual perception and interpretation of the environment. The natural need for active movement should be a kind of clue for parents to help them understand where the child is going and how to ensure his safe movement. Gaining experience through the senses is the most exciting form of activity for children.

These experiences are an extremely important element in the development of children. Everything that has been achieved with the help of the senses settles deeply in their memory and awakens in them a willingness to take responsibility, as well as teaches them to appreciate the world around them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The task of the kindergarten is to awaken the child's interest in the world around us through observation and research. It can be solved in various ways, for example: through natural contact, observing living and inanimate objects of nature; through games, imitating and distributing roles; through art, listening to relaxing music, sounds of nature, getting acquainted with albums, literature, fairy tales, as well as through creative activities with children. Below are the game options, which will make classes with children more exciting. These games can be played both in the gym and on walks.

Green corner

In order for the educator to satisfy the children's interest in the world around them, he needs to recognize that the main point in the upbringing of children is the active and independent work of the child with objects and phenomena of nature. That is why it is necessary to add a piece of nature to each class (...).

Creating a green corner is one of the forms of developing children's interest in the world around them. It can be placed in the hall, on the outdoor area, in the garden or on the windowsill. Returning from a walk or excursion, children can store various natural objects (cones, leaves, bark, dried flowers, etc.), plants, fish food, herbariums, albums, books and films about nature, audio recordings with sounds of nature and relaxing music, various auxiliary tools for observing nature (magnifying glass, telescope, magnifying glass, camera, microscope, map, thermometer, barometer, scales, set of road signs, stocks of natural materials - coal, wood, cotton). The corner is created by children. At the same time, they must systematically

replenish it together with their parents and caregivers, taking into account the time of the year, their needs and capabilities. The educator can group the available material. Every child should be able to take care of the corner. Children should share the responsibilities of caring for him among themselves. The most effective method of working with the green corner is a practical method based on observations. Children can independently, under the supervision of a tutor, make observations and experiment. In addition to the experiment, classes can be turned into a game, for example:

- grouping and classification of natural objects by composition. Selection of images for them;
- riddles about stored plants, with simultaneous demonstration of them;
- creating ikebana from various plants:
- grain crops, weeds;
- animals that live in the forest and park.
- Grouping and layout placement;
- multimedia presentation, for example, "Garden in spring". Search for fruit tree branches in a green corner;
- classification of fruit and vegetable seeds by container: sunflower, beans, melon, peas. Gluing appropriate illustrations on seed containers;
- sounds of nature: Listening and recognizing, for example, the sounds of the forest;
- birds that come to us in the spring. Presentation of albums, illustrations and listening to the sounds made by these birds;

Forest

The forest is an interesting and awakening place that, thanks to its diversity, as well as the possibility of direct contact with nature, enriches the treasury of experiences and experiences of all children.

Heike Baum

The forest is an interesting place to observe.

Due to the richness of plants and animals, the forest strip affects all organs feelings. It is necessary to plan a walk in the forest in advance and discuss its details with the children. The forest, as a place with many opportunities, becomes a kind of playground for children. It is mandatory to have and follow the rules of conduct for a walk in the forest. It is most effective to observe nature by dividing into groups, under the supervision of several adults, and then at joint meetings to exchange impressions. In order for children to satisfy their need for movement, they should be offered to play various games, for example:

- meeting with a tree. The child first chooses and then hugs the tree that he likes the most. He touches its branches and bark with his hands, and pays attention to the smell. The child can also draw a tree he likes in his notebook or album;
- a forest chest. Participants of the walk can collect forest treasures in a special box or box (under the supervision of an adult), for example, cones or leaves. At the end of the walk, the children discuss their findings among themselves;
- picnic in the forest. On specially prepared and laid out tablecloths, children together with their teachers prepare treats. At an improvised table, you can sing a song with the children or tell them a fairy tale;
- competitions in the forest. You can compete in throws for the accuracy of cones in the basket, in making crafts from cones, acorns or stones, as well as in collecting decorative autumn bouquets of leaves;
- The dance of the leaves. This is an outdoor game; children imitate leaves falling from trees;
- Hidden pictures. The teacher hides in a certain place several pictures, photographs, illustrations thematically related to the forest nature. Children are divided into groups and try to find them;

- forest men. The participants collect natural material and lay out the image of a forest man on the ground from it. The teacher photographs the resulting image;
- colors of the forest. Pupils look through a telescope (for example, through a cardboard tube after using up a paper towel) at a forest landscape. The purpose of the task is to describe all visible colors;

CONCLUSION

Thus, ecological and wellness walks contribute to a long stay of children in the fresh air, the formation of health-saving skills and ideas about a healthy lifestyle, develop mental activity, lead preschoolers to realize the need for active activities aimed at preserving health and a deeper acquaintance with nature, forming a fairly holistic view of the world around them.

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